

METHODS OF USING PRACTICAL METHODS IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS IN HIGH SCHOOLS

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Annotation: this article provides detailed information about reforms in the field of culture, art, and music in our country, methods of using various methods in music culture classes in secondary schools.

Keywords: method, lesson, student, skill, practical method, theoretical knowledge, music, musical literacy, skill.

Annotatsiya: mazkur maqolada yurtimizdagi madaniyat, san'at, musiqa sohasidagi islohotlar, umumta'lim maktablarida musiqa madaniyati darslarida turli xil metodlardan foydalanish usullari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: metod, dars, o'quvchi, malaka, amaliy metod, nazariy bilimlar, musiqa, musiqiy savodxonlik, ko'nikma.

Аннотация: в данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры, искусства и музыки в нашей стране, методах использования различных методов на уроках музыкальной культуры в общеобразовательных школах.

Ключевые слова: метод, урок, ученик, умение, практический метод, теоретические знания, музыка, музыкальная грамотность, навык.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", of May 30, 2019 "On the organization of the activities of the state museumreserves Sarmishsay", "Shakhrisabz", "Termez" and "Kokand" Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 "On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts" Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 "Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3].

One of the most urgent tasks of the personnel training system is to prepare students studying in higher educational institutions, including music teachers, who have thorough professional training and are skilled masters of their profession, based on the requirements of modern science and education. It is necessary to pay attention to their development. Practical methods consist of various activities of students in the form of exercises, as well as laboratory and

practical work. [4] These methods are used to acquire new knowledge and previously obtained. It can serve to consolidate knowledge, but its main task is to teach how to apply the acquired knowledge in practice in different situations and to create skills and competencies in students.[5] By means of practical methods, it is used to form students' vocal and choral skills, to analyze the structure and means of expression of music, to determine its genres and forms, and to learn notation. For example, in the development of vocal and choral skills, in learning notation or stepping to music, the practice method is used more often, and they are used in various types of activities. We noted above that practical methods include exercises.

In their implementation, not only verbal or visual perception of educational information takes place, but also direct application of the received theoretical knowledge in practice. It is very important to choose a structure of exercises that allows to fully ensure the practical application of the theoretical knowledge gained when using the method of practical exercises. If, for example, the rules of notation are being mastered from music literacy in the first grades, then the exercise system should fully cover the practical application of all these rules.

In this, the rules of writing the style (staff) of the note, the rule of writing the head part, the rule of writing the head and the style, the rule of writing the flag, and the rule of writing the three parts of the note are provided. In addition to integrity, the system of exercises also requires logical consistency, which means, for example, writing exercises such as writing notes between staves, on bars, under the first bar, above the fifth bar, on additional bars, each previous exercise leads to the mastery of the next exercise requires placement to aid preparation.[6]

Violation of logical consistency leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition and consolidation. When performing exercises, it is necessary to observe the following rules that ensure the effectiveness of using this type of training methods. Students should be given the clear purpose of the exercises: what knowledge to apply during the exercises, what to strengthen, what knowledge and skills need to be formed during the exercise. In vocal-choir work, methods and techniques for developing singing breath, voice production, pronunciation, pitch and ensemble skills are widely used. This includes conducting a piece of music, singing songs over and over again, comparing pieces in terms of musical structure, singing a song, vocal exercises, etc. In the practical method of teaching, vocal-choral skills are formed through the

repertoire of songs specified in the music science program and through special vocal-choral exercises that set a narrow goal. Most of the time, singing teachers do not consider vocal-choir exercises as a waste of time, they think that the work on the song alone is enough to give students vocal education. It is impossible to agree with such views. The more creative a music teacher is in choosing a special exercise, the faster he will achieve his goal. [7] Vocal-choir exercises should take a certain place in every music lesson. These exercises can be very different, but always take into account the age characteristics of the child. Vocal-choir exercises and practice-singing are important means of practical training. Laboratory and practical work consists of very diverse types of independent activities performed by students under the guidance of the teacher. It can be conducting experiments in physics and chemistry classes, performing various assignments on the spot from geography, geometry. In music lessons, students can also learn independently about the ways to perform movements to the music or the tactics of conducting a musical game. Musical play works best in elementary grades. Small musical games are learned in the classroom, and the tunes and songs learned in the classroom and which require a large space are practiced in extracurricular activities.

The main condition of the practical method is the analysis of completed exercises, practical work and their assessment. There are positive and negative aspects of musical learning skills and competencies in the lesson. It also shows typical mistakes that students make. But it is necessary to demonstrate good work in the classroom. Teaching by positive example is preferred. Students, especially teenagers, are very upset when the mistakes of their work are shown to the whole class as a bad example. If the conditions of skill formation are observed, practical methods of teaching lead to successful acquisition of educational materials.

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